

The Four-Year Ethological Study: Investigating the Symbiotic Dynamics Between Avian and Scientific Communities in an Urban Setting

Jack the Sparrow¹, Aleksandra Bielawska-Pohl² and Malgorzata Cebrat^{3*}

¹ Boxes no 6-8, Weigla 12 backyard, 513-114, Wroclaw, Poland

² Laboratory of Biology of Stem and Neoplastic Cells, Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy Polish Academy of Sciences, Weigla 12, 513-114, Wroclaw, Poland

³ Laboratory of Cellular and Molecular Immunology, Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy Polish Academy of Sciences, Weigla 12, 513-114, Wroclaw, Poland

* Correspondence: malgorzata.cebrat@hirszfeld.pl; 4871 3709980#333

Abstract: In the intricate urban fabric, where biodiversity meets scientific pursuits, this four-year survey focuses on the cohabitation dynamics within the Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy's backyard in Wroclaw, Poland. The study's origin, rooted in the dual motivation of scientific curiosity and artistic expression, led to the initiative driven by a scientist's passion for bird photography. Calendar sales financed nesting boxes, fostering a community committed to environmental stewardship. The deliberate installation of 66 nesting boxes provides a unique lens into avian behaviors. This paper elucidates methodological intricacies, data collection, and analytical frameworks, contributing to urban ecology and the intersectionality of diverse communities. Wooden nesting boxes, procured online, were categorized (A, A1, B) based on dimensions and entry features. Strategically affixed to trees, these boxes provided insight into avian nesting habits. Annual inspections, facilitated by meticulous data analysis, revealed occupancy patterns. The nesting activity, observed and categorized, showcased species-specific preferences. Beyond avian impact, the study explores reciprocal effects on human well-being, fostering awareness and connections among the scientific community. As a testament to the 'nest initiative,' the paper explores its correlation with an eco-friendly environment and the flourishing ecosystem within the Institute's backyard. While the impact on avian populations is evident, the study hints at nuanced human and ecological ramifications, setting the stage for future in-depth analyses.

Although some sentences in this paper may not appear deadly serious, the authors solemnly declare that the results presented here are based on truth and nothing but the truth.

Keywords: city, backyard, trees, birds, nests, scientists, symbiosis, lack of funding, frustration, psychological support, birdwatching

Citation: Sparrow, J. T.; Bielawska-Pohl, A.; Cebrat, M. The Four-Year Ethological Study: Investigating the Symbiotic Dynamics Between Avian and Scientific Communities in an Urban Setting *J Backyard Ornithol.* 2024, 1, 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10582063>

Academic Editor: Blue Tit

Received: 25.01.2024

Revised: 25.01.2024

Accepted: 25.01.2024

Published: 26.01.2024

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Within the multifaceted urban landscape, where the tapestry of biodiversity is interwoven with the intellectual pursuits of the scientific community, this four-year survey undertakes a comprehensive investigation. Focused on unraveling the intricate dynamics of cohabitation, the study zooms in on a shared location within the city, specifically the backyard of the Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy, Wroclaw, Poland. Noteworthy in this exploration is the deliberate installation of 66 nesting boxes, strategically positioned to provide shelter and insights into the breeding behaviors of avian inhabitants.

Cities, as evolving ecosystems, present an amalgamation of natural and intellectual diversity. In light of this, understanding the coexistence patterns between avian species and the scientific community becomes a crucial endeavor. This paper, therefore, aims to elucidate the methodological intricacies, data collection strategies, and analytical frameworks employed in the pursuit of comprehending the multifaceted interactions inherent in the four-year cohabitation survey.

The decision to install 66 nesting boxes adds a unique dimension to our study, offering a tangible platform for the avian residents to express their natural behaviors. The backyard of the Institute, now dotted with these boxes, serves as an experimental ground, providing a closer look into avian nesting habits, communal behaviors, and the potential influence of the scientific milieu on these natural processes.

As we delve into the habits, interactions, and adaptations of both avian and scientific cohorts, this study aspires to contribute not only to the understanding of urban ecology but also to the broader discourse on the intersectionality of diverse communities within shared urban spaces. The nuanced cohabitation of birds and scientists, accentuated by the presence of 66 meticulously placed nesting boxes, unfolds as a captivating exploration of the delicate balance between nature and intellect within the bustling urban ecosystem.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Nesting boxes

The wooden nesting boxes were procured from various vendors on the Allegro online shopping website. Three types of nesting boxes were installed: A, A1, and B. The outer dimensions of A and A1 boxes were 15 cm x 15 cm x 29 cm (H) with entry diameters of 3.3 cm and 2.8 cm, respectively. The distance from the entry to the bottom of the boxes was 17 cm. The dimensions of the B-type box were 17 cm x 17 cm x 40 cm (H) with an entry diameter of 4.5 cm, and the distance from the entry to the bottom of the box was 24 cm. All boxes were constructed from impregnated 2 cm-thick pine boards.

2.2. Installation of the nesting boxes

The nesting boxes were affixed to trees in the backyard of the Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy, Wrocław, Poland (51°04'39.0"N 17°01'18.3"E), positioned at a height of 2-3 meters above the ground. The entries were oriented towards quieter areas, specifically avoiding roads, parking lots, and sidewalks. To secure the boxes to the trees, 10 cm-long and 5 mm thick brass screws (from Castorama) were employed, and an electric screwdriver (from Lidl) facilitated the installation process. The use of an aluminum ladder was necessary, and great care was exercised to prevent any falls during the installation process.

2.3. Inspection of the nesting boxes

The nesting boxes were inspected annually in mid- to late winter. The front board of the boxes was temporarily removed, and if an old nest was present, it was carefully cleared, and the inner surface of the box was thoroughly cleaned. Subsequently, the front board was reattached. Special attention was given to prevent face contamination of the person(s) cleaning the nesting boxes with dry bird feces.

2.4. Data analysis

Data was acquired by taking notes during the inspections and analysed using MS Excel.

3. Results

3.1. How and why it all started

Curiosity, self-realization, self-expression, and the desire to contribute to human knowledge and history are acknowledged motivations that drive both scientists and artists. Additionally, there are hidden motivations, including the craving for validation of

one’s intellect and/or creative abilities, along with the pursuit of acknowledgment and acclaim from others, with a strong preference for the broadest possible audience. Honest acknowledgment of both types of these driving forces was the starting point for this project.

One of the authors of this paper (MC), besides being a scientist possibly undergoing a mid-life crisis, is a keen amateur birdwatcher expressing a very strong gatherer-hunter instinct which she, being a passionate opposer of hunting, channels through bird photography. After going through a phase of totally uninteresting and blurry pictures, her skills improved and crossed the threshold of self-satisfaction spiced with a pinch of vanity. In pursuit of broad recognition of her talent and passion (and not being satisfied with the ephemeral nature of social media posts), she decided to impose her bird pictures on a broad audience in the form of a calendar. The choice of this medium was well-thought through as a calendar can fit many pictures (title page + 12 months), is used (and therefore looked at) the entire year, is relatively cheap (5-7 \$), and can serve as a small gift (perfect for Christmas or St. Nicolas day). On the other hand, MC’s sensitivity and care for the well-being of wild creatures have expressed themselves in the idea of installing nesting boxes in the backyard of her workplace (Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Experimental Therapy, Polish Academy of Sciences, Wroclaw, Poland: IITD). The backyard of IITD spans an area of 7.8 hectares (Figure 1) and, most importantly, has been planted with trees about 30-40 years ago as a result of a community initiative of the Institute’s employees (led by Janusz Boratynski). Additionally, the Institute neighbors with a city park being a possible reservoir of avian population.

To fulfill both goals: recognition of her talent and installing nesting-boxes, MC decided to print calendars featuring bird pictures made by herself (picture size: A4) and use the proceeds (2-3\$/calendar) for acquiring nesting-boxes. To increase the commitment of potential buyers (or more precisely – co-founders of the initiative), she posted the pictures on social media and asked for votes for the most interesting and beautiful ones, which were subsequently used in the calendar. The response exceeded expectations – the expected satisfying result was the distribution of ~30 calendars, yet in the first year (2019), 164 calendars found their owners. Because of the high social demand, the process was repeated in the following years (2020-2023) with a significant increase in distributed calendars in 2022 and 2023, most likely attributed to word-of-mouth advertising (Table 1). To date, the total number of 922 calendars has been printed and distributed. To preserve transparency, a detailed financial report is sent every year to all interested individuals. The reports also include information about the nesting activity of the birds. To enhance the motivation to monitor results, the founders were assigned specific nesting boxes. This naturally fueled curiosity about the success of one’s nest lodgers, adding a touch of harmless rivalry among the human participants of the study.

The mean number of receivers of the calendars was 94 people each year, in total 159 distinct individuals in the 5-year period. Within this group, 52% were employees and Ph.D. students of IITD, and 48% were neighbors, friends, social media followers, and family members of MC. To the author’s satisfaction, a group of very committed recipients has established, acquiring the calendars every or almost every year (42%). A steady increase in the number of calendars acquired per person has been observed (Table 2).

Table 1. Number of nesting initiative co-founders and calendars distributed in years 2019-2023

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
number of people	92	88	81	96	112
number of calendars	164	156	159	193	250

Table 2. Number of calendars acquired by a single person in years 2019-2023

number of calendars/person	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	65	48	41	50	48
2	16	27	23	22	34
3	5	6	9	13	11
4	0	2	4	4	8
5	3	3	1	3	4
6	0	1	1	2	4
7	1	1	0	1	1
8	0	0	1	0	1
9	0	0	0	0	0
10	1	0	1	1	1
20	1	0	0	0	0

Figure 1. The localization of the nesting boxes in the backyard of Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy (V-shaped building) in nesting seasons A) 2020 and 2021, B) 2022, C) 2023

3.2. The nesting activity of birds in IITD backyard

After carefully observing the bird species visiting the backyard of IITD, three types of wooden nesting boxes were installed on the trees: A, A1, and B. A and A1 boxes are identical in size but differ in the diameter of the entrance, thus catering to specific inhabitant species. The A-type box is suitable for house sparrows (*Passer domesticus*), Eurasian tree sparrows (*Passer montanus*), and great tits (*Parus major*), while the A1 box is intended for Eurasian blue tits (*Cyanistes caeruleus*). The B-type box is larger and suitable for species such as common starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*). Boxes numbered 1-44 were installed in the year 2020, boxes 45-60 in the year 2022, and boxes 61-66 in the year 2023. During winter period following each breeding season, the nesting boxes were inspected and cleaned. The boxes were categorized as follows: 1. with nests, 2. without nests but with visible signs (feces) of occupancy, suggesting the use of the box as a night and/or winter hideout, 3. empty. The list of numbers, types, and occupancy status of the nesting boxes is presented in Table 3. Figure 1 shows the localization of the nesting boxes.

Table 3. Ordinal numbers, type and occupancy status of the nesting boxes. Green: nest, orange: occupied without nest, red: empty. Nesting boxes moved during the study are highlighted in blue.

number	type	2020	2021	2022	2023	number	type	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	A	Green	Red	Green	Yellow	35	B	Green	Green	Green	Green
2	A	Red	Green	Green	Green	36	A	Red	Green	Yellow	Yellow
3	A1	Green	Green	Red	Green	37	A	Green	Green	Green	Green
4	A	Green	Green	Green	Green	38	A	Green	Green	Green	Yellow
5	A1	Green	Green	Red	Red	39	A	Red	Green	Yellow	Yellow
6	A	Green	Green	Green	Green	40	A	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow
7	A	Green	Green	Green	Green	41	A1	Green	Green	Green	Green
8	B	Green	Green	Green	Green	42	A	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow
9	A	Red	Green	Red	Red	43	A	Red	Red	Green	Yellow
10	A	Yellow	Green	Red	Yellow	44	B	Green	Green	Green	Green
11	A	Red	Green	Green	Green	45	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Red
12	A	Green	Green	Green	Red	46	A	xxx	xxx	Yellow	Yellow
13	A1	Red	Red	Red	Red	47	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Green
14	A1	Red	Red	Green	Green	48	A	xxx	xxx	Yellow	Green
15	A1	Green	Yellow	Red	Yellow	49	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Green
16	A	Green	Red	Yellow	Green	50	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Yellow
17	A	Red	Green	Green	Yellow	51	A	xxx	xxx	Yellow	Green
18	A	Red	Green	Green	Yellow	52	A	xxx	xxx	Red	Yellow
19	B	Red	Green	Green	Green	53	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Yellow
20	A	Red	Red	Green	Yellow	54	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Green
21	A1	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	55	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Green
22	A1	Green	Green	Red	Green	56	A	xxx	xxx	Red	Green
23	A	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	57	A	xxx	xxx	Yellow	Green
24	A	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow	58	A	xxx	xxx	Yellow	Yellow
25	B	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	59	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Yellow
26	A	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	60	A	xxx	xxx	Green	Yellow
27	B	Green	Green	Green	Green	61	B	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
28	B	Green	Green	Green	Green	62	A	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
29	A1	Red	Red	Green	Yellow	63	B	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
30	A1	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	64	B	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
31	A	Red	Green	Yellow	Red	65	B	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
32	A	Red	Yellow	Green	Red	66	B	xxx	xxx	xxx	Green
33	B	Green	Green	Green	Green						
34	A	Red	Green	Yellow	Green						

While the localization of the nesting boxes usually remained unchanged throughout the study, minor adjustments were occasionally made to potentially enhance breeding success. Some nesting boxes (marked in blue in Table 3) were moved to avoid car traffic or replaced after unexplained disappearances.

Figure 2 summarizes the changes in occupancy of the nesting boxes throughout the study period. As expected, the first year brought the lowest percentage of occupied boxes, likely due to the beginning of the process of the bird population taking over the area. The overall percentage of boxes with nests was highest in the year 2021 (68%). In the following years, the occupancy of the boxes gradually dropped to 52% (Fig. 2A). This decrease may be attributed to two factors: a) the end of the relatively calm period of the Covid-19 pandemic, resulting in more traffic around the Institute, and b) the initiation of several big-scale renovation and construction initiatives in the IITD backyard (particularly at the northern side), causing traffic and noise. It is worth noting, however, that the decrease in the number of nests was likely not due to birds abandoning the area altogether, as the percentage of empty boxes also decreased while the number of boxes occupied without nests grew. We conclude, therefore, that birds are still present but find the conditions unfavorable for reproducing. This is encouraging as it leaves us hopeful that completing the construction works will result in restoring high nesting success.

The changes in nest occupancy were not uniform for every box type (Fig. 2B, C). While the percentage of A1-type boxes with nests was relatively low but stable throughout the study period, the mentioned drop in nesting success is attributed to a significant decrease in the percentage of nests in A-type boxes. This could mean that aforementioned unfavorable conditions affected mainly sparrows and great tits or worrisomely reflects the general decrease in the number of house sparrows in Poland. In contrast to A- and A1-type boxes, the B-type boxes were occupied in 100% (except the first nesting season), despite almost doubling the number of installed nesting boxes in the course of the study. We conclude that the population of starlings is thriving, much to the distress of nearby fruit-tree owners.

Figure 2. Occupancy status of the nesting boxes throughout the study. A) overall occupancy status (%), B) occupancy status of specific types of boxes (%), C) absolute number of boxes with or without nests multiplied by the number of years. Numbers inside the bars indicate the absolute number of analysed nesting boxes.

3.3. The impact of birds on the human population and the ecosystem

While the influence of the nesting box initiative on the avian population can be relatively easily monitored, the reciprocal effect— the impact of the bird population on the well-being of the human population at IITD—is more speculative, and the results are not quantified to date. Judging from the individual and subjective experiences of the human authors of this study and their close co-workers, as well as objective observations of the engagement of employees and students in the maintenance of the nesting boxes (Fig. 3A), this impact can be seen in several areas: a) raising awareness about bird species and their needs, b) creating bonds among colleagues who share a similar passion for nature, c) sense of doing something with an immediate positive impact (unlike scientific research, which is endless and its results are indefinitely postponed), d) creating a refuge for scientists frustrated with unjust reviews, unfair evaluations, unrealistic expectations of research efficiency with little to no funding and grant proposal rejections (the success rate of grant funding plummeted in Poland to a disastrous 7%). These and many other possible impacts, as suggested by the reviewers of this paper, will be analyzed in detail and published in an upcoming article. The decision to split the research into two papers was made in order to increase the number of papers in the academic curricula of the authors.

It is worth noting that the 'nest initiative' caused (or at least correlated with) general awareness to create an eco-friendly environment: the grass at the IITD backyard is not trimmed as often as usual, turning into meadows able to feed and shelter bees and birds. This resulted also in the inhabitation of the backyard by a female roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*) (Honorata) who in 2023 gave birth to two fawns (Sabina and Rudolf) (Fig. 3B). The fur of the deer(s) was found as building material of one of the nests (Fig. 3C), a fact we gladly deem as a sign of a thriving ecosystem of which we are understandably proud. Also (the first author of this paper is not at all thrilled about it!), the growing population of passerines attracts birds of prey such as common kestrels (*Falco tinnunculus*) who nest on the roof of the Institute. The Institute's backyard also hosts a small apiary (Fig. 3D) – the bees (*Apis mellifera*) take advantage of the untrimmed meadows and blooming trees but, in turn, fall victim to the European green woodpecker (*Picus viridis*) (Fig. 3E), humans stealing honey and serve as subjects of scientific research (Zareba et al. 2017, Mroczek et al. 2022, Mroczek et al. 2024). The surplus income from the calendar distribution was used to buy winter food and a feeding station for birds (Fig. 3F), three mini-hotels for wild pollinators (Fig. 3G) and will be used for planting trees (maple and linden trees). The backyard also hosts red squirrels (*Sciurus vulgaris*), red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) and European badgers (*Meles meles*) (sic!, K. Szalapata, personal communication). This species-rich ecosystem has given rise to a widely discussed proposition of organizing safari-like tours for the general public, with the proceeds subsequently used to finance scientific research at the Institute.

4. Discussion

The authors do not feel the necessity of discussing their results, as the findings are so straightforward and self-explanatory that any further comments would cloud the clear message provided above.

Figure 3. The ecosystem of the IITD backyard. A) installing and cleaning of the nesting boxes, B) Honorata the roe deer and her fawns (Rudolf and Sabina), C) a nest with roe deer fur as a building material, D) the apiary, E) the European green woodpecker and his masterpiece (created on the wall of one of the beehives), F) the feeding station for birds and the Institute, G) occupied hotel for wild pollinators. Photo: Kinga Adamczyk-Węglarzy, Sabina Koj and Małgorzata Cebart

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, J t S, M. C. ; Methodology, M. C. Formal Analysis, M. C.; Investigation, M. C., A. B-P; Resources, J t S, M. C.; Data Curation, A. B-P; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, M. C.; Writing – Review & Editing, M. C. Supervision, M. C.; Project Administration, M. C.; Funding Acquisition, M. C. and J t S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no support from public funding sources. The expenses associated with the acquisition of nesting boxes and screws were financed through proceeds generated from the sale of calendars featuring bird photographs authored by MC. The electric screwdriver was generously provided by MC, and the ladder was borrowed from the technical facility of the Institute. It is pertinent to note that the human authors did not receive any financial compensation for their contributions to this work.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: We would like to thank all people involved in the installing and annual cleaning of the boxes throughout the period of the study and taking care of other wild creatures in the backyard: Julia Tarnowska, Monika Jasek, Marta Wagner, Nafeesa Moksud, Andrzej Wiśniewski, Joanna Niedbalska-Tarnowska, Kinga Adamczyk-Węglarzy, Agnieszka Gąsiorek, Tomasz Niedziela, Sabina Koj, Robert Mroczek, Jolanta Artym and Karol Szałapata.

Special thanks are extended to Janusz Boratynski, the visionary behind the tree-planting initiative in the backyards of the Institute during the late '80s of the 20th century.

We would also like to express our gratitude to the former and current heads of the Institute, Jacek Rybka and Andrzej Gamian, for their understanding support of this and other bold initiatives. We recognize that managing a population of scientists is akin to herding cats, and we extend our appreciation for your patience in this seemingly impossible quest.

Conflicts of Interest: Jack the Sparrow declares that in the course of the study he and his extended family have taken over apartments in several of the A-type nesting boxes.

References

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/House_sparrow
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eurasian_tree_sparrow
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Great_tit
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eurasian_blue_tit
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_starling
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roe_deer
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_kestrel
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_green_woodpecker
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Western_honey_bee
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Red_fox
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Red_squirrel
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Badger>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human>

Zareba, J.; Blazej, P.; Laszkiewicz, A.; Sniezewski, L.; Majkowski, M.; Janik, S.; Cebrat, M. Uneven distribution of complementary sex determiner (*csd*) alleles in *Apis mellifera* population. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 2317, doi:10.1038/s41598-017-02629-9.

Mroczek, R.; Laszkiewicz, A.; Blazej, P.; Adamczyk-Węglarzy, K.; Niedbalska-Tarnowska, J.; Cebrat, M. New insights into the criteria of functional heterozygosity of the *Apis mellifera* complementary sex determining gene- Discovery of a functional allele pair differing by a single amino acid. *PLoS One* **2022**, *17*, 1–17, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0271922.

Mroczek, R.; Niedbalska-Tarnowska, J.; Moškrič, A.; Adamczyk-Węglarzy, K.; Laszkiewicz, A.; Cebrat, M. The Potential of Complementary Sex-Determiner Gene Allelic Diversity for Studying the Number of Patriline within Honeybee Colonies. *Appl. Sci.* **2024**, *14*, 26.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/app14010026>